

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS ONE OF THE NEW FIELD OF LINGUISTICS

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ANNOTATION: Language and humanity are the same part of life as language is developed with humans. Language is changed as humans are changed. There are a great number of languages and they have their own rules. Linguoculturology connects all languages as it shows some differences and similarities between languages. The article describes linguoculturology and its origin as well as some scientists who added their contribution to the linguistics.

KEY WORDS: linguistics, linguoculturology, language, culture, cognition

Nowadays, the science of "Cognitive Linguistics" has become very popular in linguistics. This subject is one of the most relevant areas of linguistics, which has a strong place in modern linguistics. Since this subject is very interesting for me, I got my scientific work from this subject. The topic of my dissertation is "Linguo-cognitive aspect of color conceptosphere representation in English and Uzbek languages". Now I will inform you about the opinions of many professors about this subject.

The word cognitive is derived from the English word "cognize - to know, to understand, to understand", and this field is not limited to the theory of knowledge in philosophy, but connects language with thinking (consciousness), psychological, biological and neurophysiological aspects of its formation with social, cultural and linguistic phenomena. conducts deep scientific research of organic connection. In this respect, cognitive linguistics is connected with various fields such as psycholinguistics, anthropolinguistics, ethnoinguistics, sociolinguistics.

According to Sh. Safarov, the task of cognitive linguistics is to acquire and store knowledge with the help of language, to apply and transfer language in practice, and in general, to connect the language system and its structure with thinking as a reflection in the human brain, and to carry out in-depth scientific research.

A. Abduazizov said that the center of complex phenomena such as formation, transmission, conscious storage of speech is carried out through brain neurons. By differentiating the form and content of different units in the language, using different concepts, frames, and defining national-cultural and social features, phonological tools are of great service.

Human language is "sound" and its great importance in creating content is studied in cognitive phonetics and phonology, so it should be recognized as the main component of cognitive linguistics.

A person's reaction to everyday events is inextricably linked with the practical application of the cognitive theory of language. Already, based on our life experience, knowledge and skills gained over the years, we can think about objects, events, events that exist in reality in one way or another, and based on this, we achieve the fluency of our speech in the process of conversation.

It is known that cognitive activity begins with a person's direct perception and feeling of reality. Sensual perception prepares the ground for the formation of the symbol of this fragment of reality in thought. In the process of perception of reality, a subject-object relationship based on a specific mutual opposition between the performer of cognitive activity and the object of this activity occurs. All stages of cognitive activity are based on the same relationship.

In modern linguistics, the cognitive direction is closely related to the analyzes at the lexical-semantic level, according to which language is a general cognitive mechanism, and a system of signs that performs the function of information presentation, code transmission and transformation in the form of a cognitive weapon.

In cognitive linguistics, mechanisms of full acquisition of information are studied with the help of cognitive structure and methods characteristic of a person. After all, words expressing intensity also serve to express knowledge and imagination about existence.

In order to understand the meaning of a word, we only need to know its semantic structure. We should also be aware of the features of thinking, ways of thinking and knowing the world with the help of language elements of people who speak a certain language. Because it is difficult to assign these tasks to a purely linguistic analysis of words. In order to better understand the nature and essence of the language phenomenon, it is necessary to put on the agenda of our research the issues related to the speaker's knowledge of existence and "cooking" it in his mind and freely conveying it to the listener in his language (speech).

The language of the literary and artistic works of that period can be studied in order to scientifically research the state of the language in a certain historical period, the features specific to that state, lexical, phonetic and grammatical differences, common and different aspects of the language with the current state. In this case, the language of artistic works and written monuments serves only as material for research with the same purpose.

Linguistics is a relatively new branch of linguistics studies the interaction and interaction of culture. Current modern in linguistics, it is important to study the influence of language and culture on each other became. The reason for this is the globalization of global problems the need to take into account the universal and unique characteristics and relationships of different peoples when solving various issues, intercultural. Anticipate situations where there is a high probability of misunderstandings the need to know, the cultural assets underlying communicative activity is the importance of definition and definition.

The connection between language and culture was first established at the beginning of the 20th century defined in the scheme of the American linguist R. Lado. A and B in his scheme it was shown how communication between individuals

should take place. XX and by the 90s of the century, the science of linguo-cultural science is very important in Russian linguistics was widely studied, especially in this field by V.N. Teliya, V.V. Vorobev, N.I. Tolstoy, Works of Y. D. Apresyan, Y. A. Yakovleva, V. A. Maslova and others is significant [1-6]. They are reflected in the language in their research and are solid who shed light on the manifestation of the established folk culture. of the 20th century in the end, the following four linguistic and cultural schools were established in Moscow:

- 1) Linguistic-cultural school of Y.S. Stepanova. It is close to the theory of E. Benvenista with the methodology of this school, whose goal is to describe culture diachronically without change;
- 2) N.D. Arntyunova school. Researches the universal terms of culture found in texts belonging to different times and peoples;
- 3) V.N. Teliya school. This school is known as the Moscow school, which deals with the linguistic and cultural analysis of phraseology in Russia and abroad.
- 4) The school of linguistic and cultural studies created by V.V. Vorobev, V.M. Shaklein and others at the People's Friendship University of Russia, continuing the theory of E.M. Vereshagin and V.G. Kostomarov.

The main feature of linguistic culture is one or another phenomenon it consists of observing equally in the context of culture. The main object of Lingvokulturology is culture and language in the process of activity Linguistic data on interconnection, interaction, and an overview of this interaction based on learning as a whole systematic integrity. Language units, elements of speech activity and human speech behavior is involved, through cultural factors is determined, and this issue, in turn, affects the cultural semantics of language signs includes.

All in all, linguculturology is a study of linguistics and culture together. It is widely used among cultures and it is easy to understand the linguistic phenomenas.

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